

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LIFE ORIENTATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article describes the results of an empirical study of the life, meaning, and value orientations of Uzbek students in the context of sociocultural changes in modern society. Data analysis revealed that the "Converter" and "Harmonizer" life orientation types predominate among students, along with an average level of meaningfulness in life, as determined by D. A. Leontiev's methodology. This is characteristic of student-age students due to their active search for personal meaning and life goals. Data analysis using Sh. Schwartz's methodology revealed the leading values of independence, kindness, and achievement. This reflects the trend of developing an individual-humanistic worldview among modern Uzbek students, combining the desire for self-realization with the preservation of traditional values. The results of the study have practical implications for the design and implementation of psychological support programs for students.*

Keywords: *life orientations, meaning-in-life orientations, value orientations, student age.*

Introduction

The implementation of the "Uzbekistan 2030" strategic program has led to large-scale transformations that have encompassed all areas of public relations in the country. Citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan live in a context of continuous socioeconomic, political, and cultural change aimed at improving the well-being of the population, strengthening democratic institutions, modernizing society, and adapting to globalization processes. Consequently, the current sociocultural situation in Uzbekistan is characterized by an intensive transformation of value systems, the expansion of educational and professional opportunities for young people, and the search for new meaningful orientations [11]. In this context, studying the life and value orientations of modern students—the most dynamic segment of the population and one most receptive to social change—is particularly important.

Students represent a social group actively developing their life goals and value priorities, making this age group sensitive to the influence of external and internal factors. It is during this period that the foundations of an individual's life position are laid, defining the process of self-determination [6]. The issue of life orientations has been actively explored in the works of foreign and domestic authors—V. Frankl, E. Fromm, G. Allport, L.S. Vygotsky, S.L. Rubinstein, D.A. Leontiev, S. Schwartz, K.A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, E.Yu. Korzhova, A.A. Grachev, and others. However, modern sociocultural processes require a rethinking of previously obtained data in relation to the new conditions of the development of the student environment in Uzbekistan.

Despite a significant number of studies devoted to the problem of the semantic structures of the life path and individual values, the relationship between the life, life-purpose, and value orientations of students in Uzbekistan in the context of a rapidly changing society, in which digitalization and cultural integration are intensifying, remains insufficiently studied. These trends

necessitate a reconsideration of traditional life priorities and reinforce the importance of personal self-determination.

The aim of this study is to identify the characteristics of the life orientation system of students in Uzbekistan. The need for this study stems from the contradiction between society's growing demand for a harmoniously developed, value-oriented individual and the insufficient empirical study of the structure of students' life orientations in the contemporary socio-cultural context of Uzbekistan. The scientific and practical significance of this study lies in identifying general and specific trends in the development of life orientations and value systems among young people studying at branches of foreign universities in Uzbekistan. The novelty of this study lies in its comprehensive approach to studying the life, meaning, and value orientations of students in the context of a modern intercultural educational environment, which allows us to identify the specifics of their personal and value-based self-determination.

Research Methodology

The empirical study was conducted at the Tashkent branch of the A.I. Herzen State Pedagogical University of Russia. Seventy-five students (15 boys and 60 girls) aged 18 to 26, pursuing full-time undergraduate studies in the humanities and pedagogical fields, participated in the study. The study was conducted during 2025 and included several sequential stages:

1. The ascertainment stage – a survey among students using three psychodiagnostic methods.
2. The analytical stage – primary statistical processing and systematization of the obtained data.
3. The interpretative stage – a qualitative analysis of the results.

To achieve this goal, a set of psychodiagnostic methods was used to study the life, meaning, and value orientations of the student's personality:

1. The Life Orientation Questionnaire by E.Yu. Korzhova to identify the leading type of life orientation. Based on the results, respondents were classified into five types: Transformer, Harmonizer, User, Consumer, and Mixed. Interpretation was based on the typology developed by E. Yu. Korzhova (2006) [5].

2. D. A. Leontiev's Meaningful Life Orientations Test (MLOT). This method allows one to assess the overall level of meaningfulness in life and the severity of its structural components: "Purpose of Life," "Life Process," "Life Effectiveness," "Locus of Control — Self," and "Locus of Control — Life" [8].

3. S. Schwartz's Method for Studying Value Orientations. Two forms of this method were used:

- Values Survey — assessing the significance of 57 basic values.
- Portrait Value Questionnaire — assessing the respondent's compliance with 40 descriptions of personal characteristics [4].

Processing the results allowed us to identify priority values and a hierarchy within the system of normative and behavioral orientations. Descriptive statistics methods were used for the quantitative analysis: calculating arithmetic means (M) and percentage distributions. The results were visualized in tables and diagrams. The analysis followed the principles of comparing data from various methods to identify common trends and differences between groups.

Key Results

The distribution of respondents by life orientation type is presented in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Table 1 — Life Orientation Types (E.Yu. Korzhova)

№	Life Orientation	Type Quantity
1	Converter	23
2	Harmonizer	19
3	Mixed	19
4	User	9
5	Consumer	5

Fig. 1. Distribution of types of life orientations (according to E. Yu. Korzhova)

Average scores for the main scales of D.A. Leontiev's Meaning in Life Orientations Test (MOL) are presented in Table 2. The table clearly demonstrates differences across the "Purpose in Life," "Life Process," and "Life Effectiveness" scales, as well as locus of control indicators.

Table 2 — Average scores for the MOL scales (D.A. Leontiev)

№	Scale	Average value
1	Purpose in Life	31,5
2	The Process of Life	29,9
3	Life Effectiveness	25,6
4	Locus of Control - Self	20,3
5	Locus of Control - Life	29,5
6	Overall Meaningfulness of Life	100,6

Figure 2 shows the percentage ratio of students' levels of meaningfulness in life.

Fig. 2. Levels of meaningfulness in students' lives (D.A. Leontiev)

Рис. 1. Уровни осмысленности жизни

Table 3 presents the summarized results of Sh. Schwartz's methodology. The diagram reflects the students' leading value priorities based on the combined data from both parts of the methodology.

Table 3 - Average values of core values (Sh. Schwartz)

№	Value	Average
1	Independence	5,22
2	Kindness	4,64
3	Achievement	4,53
4	Universalism	4,46
5	Hedonism	4,40
6	Stimulation	4,36
7	Security	4,30
8	Conformity	4,11
9	Power	3,53
10	Tradition	3,49

Discussion

The obtained results allow us to consider the system of life, meaning, and value orientations of Uzbek students as a multicomponent psychological entity reflecting the characteristics of their personal and cultural self-determination in modern society. Data analysis using E. Yu. Korzhova's methodology revealed that the "Converter" and "Harmonizer" life orientation types predominate in the sample, demonstrating young people's desire for an active life position, internal self-regulation, and personal growth. The "User" and "Consumer" types are significantly less represented, reflecting a trend toward a decline in utilitarian attitudes and an increased interest in self-realization and inner harmony. This distribution correlates with the general focus of societal reforms aimed at developing the individual as the subject of change, and also confirms E. Yu. Korzhova's conclusions regarding the connection between life orientations and the value-motivational sphere. Results from D. A. Leontiev's Life-Meaning Orientations Test revealed a predominance of the average level of meaningfulness in life (49.3% of the sample), indicating an active search for personal meaning, characteristic of adolescence, which coincides with the student stage of life.

High levels of meaningfulness (32%) are observed in students with a pronounced sense of purpose and internal responsibility for their own lives, while low levels (18.7%) are associated with instability of life plans and uncertainty of life prospects. This distribution is consistent with D. A. Leontiev's concept, according to which, during professional development, an individual goes through a stage of developing meaningful structures aimed at integrating life experience and recognizing life goals. Data from Sh. Schwartz's method revealed that the students' leading values are independence ($M = 5.22$), kindness ($M = 4.64$), and achievement ($M = 4.53$). The prevalence of these values indicates a desire for independence, social responsibility, and self-development. At the same time, the values of authority ($M = 3.53$) and tradition ($M = 3.49$) are less pronounced, reflecting a shift away from hierarchy and reliance on external authorities in favor of individual choice.

These results are consistent with international research by S. Schwartz and domestic data on the transformation of youth value priorities toward individualism, self-realization, and tolerance. Taken together, the obtained results demonstrate that the life and value orientations of

Uzbek students are shaped in the context of intercultural interaction and the modernization of society, where traditional collectivist attitudes are gradually giving way to individually oriented models of self-determination. At the same time, the importance of humanistic values—kindness, mutual assistance, responsibility—remains significant, reflecting a cultural synthesis of traditional and modern worldviews. Of particular interest is the relationship between life orientation types and the level of meaningfulness in life: "Transformers" and "Harmonizers" often report high levels of meaningfulness and a pronounced emphasis on independence and achievement, while "Consumers" and "Users" report lower levels of semantic integration and a focus on security and conformity.

These data support the hypothesis of a systemic relationship between life and value-semantic structures of personality, outlined in the concepts of E. Yu. Korzhova and D. A. Leontiev. Thus, student youth in Uzbekistan demonstrate a balanced combination of the desire for self-realization and the preservation of social values, reflecting the specific nature of society's transitional stage—from traditionally collectivist to individualistic humanistic orientations. The psychological content of students' life orientations can be viewed as an indicator of their personal maturity and readiness to make a conscious choice of life path in the context of cultural modernization.

Conclusion

The study revealed the specifics of the life, meaning, and value orientations of Uzbek students in the context of the modern sociocultural space. The results confirmed that the structure of life orientations in college students reflects the process of actively developing life goals, value priorities, and meaning-based attitudes that determine the individual trajectory of self-development. The predominance of the "Converter" and "Harmonizer" types indicates young people's desire for independence, activity, and inner integrity, indicating the presence of an internal motivation for personal growth and self-realization.

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